

ETHNO BOTANICAL USES OF SOME PLANTS USED BY ADIVASI TRIBES OF INDERVELLY MANDAL ADILABAD DISTRICT, ANDHRA PRADESH, INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Ethno medicinal survey in IndervellymandalAdilabad District, Andhra Pradesh, which is mainly occupied with adivasitribes revealed that some less known medicinally important plants have been used by Tribal community as reported by 9 traditional healers of age 45-85yrs. In the present study, family name, scientific name, vernacular name, habit, useful parts were used.. In the present study a number of plants have been documented which are used by adivasi tribes of IndervellymandalAdilabad District against different disease.From the present analysis and investigation plant parts used mere roots, stem, bark, leaves, seeds and flowers. The present study concludes that, the tribes of Indervellymandal used the pharmacognostic values of these plants. Such proven plant species may be used in the formulation of new drugs against different ailments. Hence, there is great need of cultivation and conservation of such ethno medicinal plants and at the same time there is an immediate need of indigenous practices, knowledge of such plant resources and documentation.

Key words : Ethnobotany, Indervelly, Telangana, Adilabad

INTRODUCTION

According to WHO (World Health Organization) , 70% of the world population of the world depend on traditional healthcare for treatment of various diseases WHO,(2002). Traditional knowledge is deeply associated with biological resources, and an important aspect of primitive cultural groups is grow close interdependence with the environment, which also covers vast and varied scopes of knowledge from time immemorial. Folk people live mainly in less accessible and isolated areas, and used to manage their livelihood directly from forests and land. The indigenous botanical knowledge of ethnic communities relating to the uses and

management of wild plant resoures is extensive Cotton (1992), Balick (1996).

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The objective of the present study was to collect medicinal plants used in traditional medicine and folk medicine in Adilabad district of Andhra Pradesh, India.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Characteristics of the Study Area

Adilabad which is the fifth largest district in Andhra Pradesh which lies between Yavatmal (Maharashtra) bound 19 ° 29 '31.24° N latitudes' and 78 ° 40'9.4 E longitudes .it on north on the east by chanda Maharashtra State. About 60 percent of the district is inhabited by the tribal population and with regards to forest area, 46.2% is covered by dry deciduous type. Adilabad district is administratively divided into 52 mandals with 1,748 revenue villages and 7 municipalities .Tribal population is dominated by Gonds (51%), Lambada(21%), Kolam(8%) and others(8%) (Viz, Andhi ,Koya, Manne, Naikpod, Pardhan, Porja).The flora is endowed with rich diversity of medicinal plants which are used by common people of the region the region have large number of plant species with wide range of diversity and distribution Ethnomedicinal knowledge of tribals was

documented by arranging frequent field visits to the study area. The areas were visited annually for 2-3 times during the year 2012 and 2013. Extensive field trips were organized for collecting plant species present in Table-1, the data using an integrated approach of botanical collection, interviews and questionnaires to person and herbal healers the uses of plant is compare with the use of same plant by the tribes of different villages. During field survey the tribals were contacted and take to field for collecting details information about medicinal plant local names and plant parts used methods of preparation of herbal medicine and approximate dosage of administration collected datas were recorded in the field note book and herbarium were prepared.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Efficacy of different medicinal plants varies from plants to plants and part to parts (root , stem, leaves bark, seeds) depends upon their molecular properties. Medicinal plants are used in ailments in the form of paste, powder , raw form and decoction by the people of Gunnar village .It was found that 57 plant species belonging to genera

Table 1-plants used for the treatment of various disorders by the Gujjar village of sub-Himalayan tract in Aliabad district

S. No	Family / Scientific Name	Vernacular name / Habit	Uses
1	<i>Bauhimiavahliiwight</i>	Arnaddaku & / gaint climber	leaves making of leaf plates.
2	<i>Bambusa vulgaris</i>	Bambu	Hand fan
3	<i>Acanthaceae</i> <i>Adhatodavasicanees</i>	Addasaram /Shrub	Fresh leaf decoction take internally for . cough and cold
4	<i>Acantheceae</i> <i>Andrographispaniculata (Brum.f)</i> <i>Wallich ex Nees</i>	nelavemu/herb	leaf paste is applied externally for skindisease and antifungal activities.
5	<i>Aizoaceae</i> <i>Trianthemaportulacastrum L.</i>	Tellagalijeru / Prostrate herb	whole plant leucorrhoea used for
6	<i>Amaranthaceae</i> <i>Amaranthusspinosus L.</i>	Mullathotakura /Herb	Plant decoction used for dycentery
7	<i>Anacardiaceae</i> <i>Mangiferaindica L.</i>	Mamidi/Tree	Leaf juice is used for menstrual pain and Diarrhoea.
8	<i>Apiaceae</i> <i>Trachyspermumammi</i>	Vaamu/Herb	seeds are used for cold and cough
9	<i>Apiceae</i> <i>Centellaasiatica (L) Urbon</i>	Saraswathi/ prostate Climber	leaves in used for skin disease galacogogue

10	<i>Aristolochiaceae</i> <i>Aristolochiaindica L.</i>	Nnalleshwari/Climber	Roots used for snake bite and leucoderma
11	<i>Asclepiadaceae</i> <i>Cakitrions gigantean (l.) Dryand</i>	Tellajelledu/Shrub	latex applied on wounds, rheumatic pains
12	<i>Asclepiadaceae</i> <i>Pergulariadaemia</i>	Dustaputega/Shrub	Stem juice is used to cure jaundice
13	<i>Asteraceae</i> <i>Eclipta prostrate L.</i>	Guntagalagara/Herb	whole plant is used fruits cut and wounds
14	<i>Asteraceae</i> <i>Tridaxprocumbens L.</i>	Nallalam/ herb	Leaf juice is applied externally for healing wounds
15	<i>Asteraceae</i> <i>Vernoniacinerea (L.) less</i>	Sahadevi/ Herb	Root used rheumatism and high fever
16	<i>Caesalpinceae</i> <i>Cassia occidendtalis</i>	Kasinth Shrub	Seed and leaf pate applied externally in skin diseases leucoderma
17	<i>Caesalpinaceae</i> <i>Bauhinia purrea L.</i>	Devakanchanam/Tree	Bark juice with honey is taken orally against leucorrhoea.
18	<i>Caesalpinaceae</i> <i>Cassia tora L.</i>	Thagarisa/ Herb	Leaf paste used for skin diseases
19	<i>Caricaceae</i> <i>Carica papaya L.</i>	Bopayee	taken orally for abortion
20	<i>Combretaceae</i> <i>Terminaliachebularelz.</i>	Karakkaya/Tree	Fruit is used for cough and diarrhoea
21	<i>Combretaceae</i> <i>Diosprosmelauoxylon Roxb</i>	Thuniki tree	leaf, fruits leaf making Indian cigarette (beedi)
22	<i>combretaceae</i> <i>Terminaliapallida</i>	Tella karaka tree	fruits are used for diarrhorrha, cough, cold.
23	<i>Euphorbaceae</i> <i>Euphorbia hirta L.</i>	Pachabotlu / Herb	whole plant used for jaundice. Leaf used for dysentery
24	<i>Euphorbiaceae</i> <i>Phyllanthusemblica L.</i>	Usiri/ Tree	Fruits are taken to cure dysentery
25	<i>Fabaceae</i> <i>Buteamonosperma L.</i>	Modhuga/tree	Making of leaf plates flowers are used for dye
26	<i>Fabaceae</i> <i>AbrusprecatiuisL.</i>	Gurvinda/ Climber	Seeds used for snake bite
27	<i>Fabaceae</i> <i>Pongamiapinnata (L) pierre</i>	Kanuga/Tree	Oil extracted from seeds is used for skin disease & Leucoderma
28	<i>Lamiaceae</i> <i>Leucasaspera(willd).Link</i>	Thummi/Herb	Leaf juice taken orally for menstrual pains and jaundice.
29	<i>Lamiaceae</i> <i>Ocimum sanctum L.</i>	Thulasi /herb	Root is against snake bite. Leaf juice is taken cough and fever.
30	<i>Lamiaceae</i> <i>Anisomelesindica(L.)kuntze</i>	China ranaberi/herb	Roots used for snake bite
31	<i>Lamiaceae</i> <i>Leonotisnepetifolia (L.) R. Br ./</i>	Ranaberi /Herb	whole plant leaf rheumatic pains
32	<i>Liliaceae</i> <i>Aloe vera(L.) Burm.f</i>	Kalabandha/herb	Stem jelly take internally for dissolve uterus cysts

33	<i>Malvaceae</i> <i>Abutilon indicum (L.) sweet</i>	Athibala herb	Root decoction taken internally for regularity in menstrual cycle
34	<i>Malvaceae</i> <i>Hibiscus rosainensis L.</i>	Mandara/ Shrub	Flower is used for irregular menstruation trouble
35	<i>Malvaceae</i> <i>Sidarhombifolia L.</i>	Athibala/Herb	Root used for rheumatism
36	<i>Meliaceae</i> <i>Azadirachtaindica A juss</i>	/ Vepa /Tree	Leaf paste and seedoil is applied externally for skin diseaseflower decoction used for jaundice
37	<i>Menispermaceae</i> <i>Tinosporacordifolia (willd.)Miers</i>	Thippathega /Climber	decoction of stem in fever
38	<i>Mimosoideae</i> <i>Acacia nilotica (L.) subspindica</i>	/ Nallathumma/ tree	Gum is used in the treatment of diarrhea.
39	<i>Mimosoideae</i> <i>Mimosa pudica L.</i>	Lajjavathi /Herb	Whole plant used for fever root diarrhea.
40	<i>Moraceae</i> <i>Ficusreligiosa L.</i>	Raavi/Tree	Bark decoction is used as leucorrhoea
41	<i>Moraceae</i> <i>Ficusrecemosa L.</i>	Medi/ Tree	The latex of the stem is useful in the treatment of wounds and diarrhea.
42	<i>Moraceae</i> <i>FicushispidiaL.f.</i>	Brahma medi/tree	Leaf powder used for leucoderma, latex wounds
43	<i>Moringaceae</i> <i>Moringaoleifera</i>	Munaga /tree	Bark used for paralysis,boiledleafrype.fruit take internally to cure eye diseases
44	<i>Musaceae</i> <i>Musa paradisiacal L.</i>	Arati / stem	Unripe fruit taken orally cure dysentery
45	<i>Nyctaginaceae</i> <i>Boerhaviadiffusa L.</i>	Atukamamidi /Climber	fresh leaf juice used for menstruation trouble, root used in jaundice
46	<i>Pedaliaceae</i> <i>Sesamumindicum(L.)</i>	Nallanuvulu Seed	with jaggary paste take orally cure in monopause.
47	<i>Plumbaginaceae</i> <i>Plumbagozelyanical L.</i>	Chitramulam	whole plant used fo skindeseases and leucoderma.
48	<i>Poaceae</i> <i>Aristidaadsensionsis L.</i>	/ cheepurugaddhi / herb	making broomstick
49	<i>Poaceae</i> <i>Cynodondactylon</i>	Garika/Herb	whole plantused forskin diseases and wound healing
50	<i>Rutceae</i> <i>Aeglemarmelos(L.)</i>	Maredu /Tree	Fresh fruit pulp take internally to cure diarrhoea
51	<i>Sapindaceae</i> <i>Cardiospearumhalicacabun L.</i>	ButtaTega/ Climber	Root ,fruit used for leucorrhoea .
52	<i>Schum&Thorn</i> <i>Phyllanthusamarus</i>	Nelausiri /Herb	whole plant extract mixed with cow milk used for Jaundice

53	<i>Symplocaceae</i> <i>Symplocosracemosa</i> Roxb.	Lodduga/tree	Steam bark used for menorrhagia
54	<i>Steame&Mabb/ verbanaceae</i> <i>Rolthecaserrata</i> (L.)	Gantabarangi/ herb	root used for menstrual disorders
55	<i>varaculeate</i> <i>Lantana camera</i> L.	Verbenaceae herb	leaf are used in fresh cut and wounds
56	<i>Vetaceae</i> <i>Cissusvitiginea</i> L.	Adavigummadi /Climber	Leaf used for wounds
57	<i>Zingiberaceae</i> <i>Curcuma longa</i> L.	Pasupu Rhizome	paste is applied for healing of wounds
58	<i>Zingiberaceae</i> <i>Zingiberofficinale</i>	Allam/ Rhizome	Rhizome decoction with honey take orally for cold and cough & digestion
59	<i>Zygophyllaceae</i> <i>Tribulesterrestris</i> L.	Palleru /Prostrate herb	Whole plant Used formenoroagia.

and families with their therapeutic values against different diseases occurring in Gunnar village. Of these species are herbs, shrubs and trees. It was found that herbs are more useful a followed by shrub and trees.

During the survey , plant and plant parts used as medicine for the treatment of various ailments like cold, cough, fever, diarrhoea, Snakebite, jaundice, rheumatism, eye diseases ,dysentery gynoec disorders wounds skin diseases have been document presented in table

The plant species are alphabetically enumerated with their plant name. Family, vernacular name habit and uses.

CONCLUSION

The present investigation is an attempt to document important traditional herbal formulations used by traditional practitioners for the treatment of various ailments and diseases

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